

TOOLPATH STRATEGY & GENERATION FOR ROBOTIC FIBRE PLACEMENT ON CURVED SURFACES

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ABSTRACT

Traditionally, manual-layup technique is used for the manufacturing of composite parts and laminates. Although this technique has its advantages, many of its disadvantages, which include the process being labour-intensive and slow, translates to high production costs. These drawbacks were later overcome with advancements in the field of automation through the introduction of the automated or robotic fibre placement (AFP/RFP) technology. The ability to orient continuous fibres in multiple directions in a precise manner is a noteworthy advantage of the AFP technology, although the technique itself presents challenges. Thus, it is essential that the fibre placement technique is precise and accurate to effectively produce components of complex geometries. In this paper the authors present an approach to use AFP technology to fabricate composites with curvatures, through path planning and placement control of continuous fibres. Particularly, research and development of a toolpath algorithm and its optimization for fibre layup on freeform curved surfaces is conducted. The various stages of the placement process or computational design methodology used in this approach are described, beginning with digital path planning and modelling, followed by programming and simulation, and concluding with tool path generation, and physical part fabrication. The research demonstrates how composites having similar curved contours can be processed with AFP.

1 INTRODUCTION

Conventionally, composite laminates or components are produced either by resin transfer moulding (RTM) or in a three-step process where pre-impregnated unidirectional carbon fibre sheets are laid onto moulds to form a desired shape. RTM involves the transfer of resin into a closed system, with dry fibres laid over a mould with the intended component shape. In both the above-mentioned processes, the prepared wet composite, then undergoes a curing process to harden (under pressure and heat) in an autoclave [1], and finally goes through a series of non-destructive quality assessing investigations. Due to the number of limitations and drawbacks imposed by these processes, which include large amounts of material wastage, limited suitability to produce complex curvature shapes, etc, alternative manufacturing technologies were introduced. These include the automated tape placement (ATP) technology and the robotic or automated fibre placement (RFP/AFP) technology. The main difference between the above two types of placement technologies, is in the form and size of composite material used. ATP uses prepreg tapes of large sizes (>50mm widths), while RFP uses tows or towpregs which are within 1 inch in width. Robotic fibre placement technology offers many advantages over the former mentioned manufacturing methods, mainly due to its use of robotic manipulators. Primarily, it offers flexibility in orienting the placement process, thereby catering to the fabrication of complex shaped composites.

Coriolis, Electroimpact and Broetje-Automation Composites are some of the few commercial manufacturers of AFP machines. They too have moved towards the development of newer machines based on industrial robotic systems, with the target of reducing the usually required large size of production space, thereby reducing manufacturing costs [2], as well as improving production flexibility. In other words, employment of robots in such systems provide the added advantage of being able to use their axes of freedom to position the fibre placement head (FPH) to extreme/critical angles as per required to lay fibres in negative features.

Robotic operations usually demand well-generated tool paths for accurate execution, especially in applications requiring tool manoeuvres over complex shapes. Although, path generation techniques and algorithms for flat parts have been attempted with much success [3], algorithms focused at curved surfaces are limited or kept as industrial secrets. This paper attempts to provide a simple tool for trajectory generation on freeform curved surfaces.

From previous studies, three noteworthy approaches to fibre path generation were identified. They are (a) simulation-based generation technique, (b) fibre steering technique and (c) sensory-based surface following technique [4]. Fibre steering involves the placement of fibres along or in the shape of an arc on a flat surface, to eventually form a curved part. Sensor-based surface following technique makes use of sensors mounted on the compaction roller to get pressure sensitive contact-based feedback for path generation. While simulation-based generation technique which is the most closely suited for our application (which is targeted at curved surfaces), due to its model-based approach, involves the creation of virtual models within relative distances to compute and generate motion paths. Simulation-based path generation approach is used in this study. The aim of the paper is to provide an algorithm to generate toolpaths for layup of pre-impregnated unidirectional towpregs (prepregs slit into narrow tows) on curved surfaces.

2 FIBER PLACEMENT SETUP

The experimental setup consists of a 6-axis industrial arm robot from KUKA and the fibre placement head (FPH) from Broetje-Automation Composites. Figure 1 shows the setup of the robotic fiber placement process.

Figure 1: Robotic fibre placement setup.

The dispensing process in the FPH begins with the feeding of uni-directional pre-impregnated tows (of compatible sizes), that are stored in the spool, into the system by the driving unit through a series of rollers. Figure 2 shows the internal diagram of the fibre placement head assembly. The tows then make their way past the built-in cutting unit to the exit, where depending on the resin system or content of the towpreg (thermoplastic or thermosetting) and their recommended curing or heat requirements, tows are either heated using the heating source (Infrared lamp) or simply laid onto a substrate/table. The substrate or table may also be heated and maintained at a certain temperature, to promote adhesion during the layup process. Both forms of heating mentioned earlier assist in bringing the tows to a partial cure state giving them their tacky property [5]. Depending on the type of towpreg used, either one or both heating methods are implemented. Tows are then cut at programmed instances to achieve any required or desired tow length.

Also present in the FPH is a cooling unit, in order to reduce the tackiness of thermosetting tows as they move through the system until before exiting the head (between the heating unit and the compaction roller), just before layup. It is essential that the entire FPH is enclosed and maintained at a temperature below 20°C.

The compaction roller applies pressure or force, to adhere tows to the surface of the substrate or mould as well as to previously laid tows, removing any trapped air or voids, thereby consolidating tows to one another. The whole process is then repeated to lay more tows and multiple layers in different directions. Finally, after curing the layup in a composite oven (requiring only vacuum bagging of laminates), composite parts are fabricated.

Of the control parameters that can be set during the fibre placement process, power of the IR heating source and the compaction force, are the most influential. Heating of the tows lower the viscosity of the resin promoting tackiness and bonding, while proper and enough compaction force prevents residual stresses, air pockets and voids in the laminates.

Figure 2: Components of the fibre placement head.

Another important feature of the FPH is its interchangeable elastomeric rollers, that allow for tows of varying sizes ranging from 1/8" (3.125mm) to 1" (25.4mm) to be used for layup. The narrower the tows, the better the layup on sharp and complex curved surfaces.

3 PATH ALGORITHM AND GENERATION FOR CURVED SURFACES

Majority of the planning is carried out using Computer-aided design (CAD) modelling features and techniques. The approach taken towards path planning and generation in this study is highly dependent on the flexibility and freedom of coding available from the chosen CAD software. Target points of interests include points to command motion paths, points at which cutting of tows are performed, and start and end points of each course of tow to be placed. Quality of the product obtained is assessed based on the tows placed, which in turn highly depends on how well the tool path is generated.

3.1 Offline Programming

Before the introduction of offline programming, programs were generated through various analytical approaches, some involving the use of a syntaxer which are structures that had to be closely modelled to the robotic structure and placed strictly at the same positions, in the robot operated setup [6]. Data obtained from the robot, which mimicked positions of the syntaxer would then be used to generate and execute operations. Another common approach was manual programming of targets through use of a teach pendant, that was introduced later in the years, to assist programmers and ease their way into the whole programming experience. However, this approach also eventually increased programming times for applications such as arc welding, thereby giving way to a much efficient method - offline programming.

Offline programming method involves the modelling of the entire work environment precisely in a computable design platform, which then is used to simulate work poses and paths that mimic actual workflows. This programming approach decreased the overall programming time required and provided better visual simulations of the process, as well as further improved and enforced better risk assessment-based protocols to avoid human injuries. However, the effectiveness of this programming approach is highly dependent on the geometric accuracy of the models within the modelling environment that represent the robot and the other hardware, as well as their respective positions in the actual work space (with a certain level of allowable tolerance depending on the application). Therefore, it is essential that the modelled environment is as accurate and close to the actual setup.

In this study, the entire working environment was modelled in rhinoceros. Codes generated using the above conditions were simulated and tested repeatedly to complete a calibration process, followed by an accuracy and repeatability check, before the actual intended operations (both simulation and practical) were attempted.

3.2 Path Strategy

Generally, in robotic applications, there are objectives that can be composed of various criteria. One such important criterion to consider in operations involving tool manipulation, is the possibility of tool solicitation during the process, if the toolpath is not at least continuous in curvature. Experimental studies have shown that this can be reduced if the toolpath is of smooth and continuous curvature [7].

Hence, the path algorithm or strategy used for the curved surface in this study was performed using the “projection technique” easily available as tools or features in most CAD software. There are many types of curves (geodesic, isoparametric, plane intersection, etc) that can be used to represent paths, each offering their advantages, such as the minimization of steering through the use of geodesic curves [8,9] and the control of gaps between consecutive tows using parallel curves [10].

For our study, the intended orientation, angle and direction of fibre placement is sketched out in the form of straight parallel lines onto a flat surface or plane and projected onto the curved surface. This gives the path pattern (location of the centreline of the tows to be placed) to be followed by the FPH during the fibre placement operation in the form of polylines or curves that have control points associated with them. These curves themselves are used to identify target points at which tows are to be cut using the FPH's "minimum tow length" as its "distance to cut at" parameter. While their control points are used as target points to command motion from target to target in the form of a trajectory. Figure 3 shows the projection of layup lines in 45, -45, 90 and 0-degree orientations on to the curved surface (red).

The list of all target points obtained (both the motion commanding points and the tow cut points) from the earlier step is then sorted into a sequence with “target points” in the first course of tow to be placed, indexed one after the other with the “tow cut point” in between them. This is followed by the next set of “target points” forming the second course of tow to be placed and so on. An optional step is to add or increase the number of points at complex intersections where increasing the resolution would improve the overall flow of the fibre placement process.

Figure 3: Projection of layup lines on to the complex curved surface.

3.3 Path Design and Modelling

In the path design step, two 3D vectors are constructed at each point on the list of targets. One vector is oriented tangent to the trajectory curve (at that target point) and the other is set normal to the surface of the part. These planes together form a 3D frame that orients and positions the compaction roller of the FPH, accurately to apply optimum perpendicular force at each point during the fibre placement process. This is achieved by constructing a sequence of frames following the desired tow trajectories.

Following this step, additional target points are also generated and added to the list of targets, to command motions to intermediate points or fly-through positions during the fibre placement process (the move from end point of one course to start point of the next course). Also added to this list of targets are points that represent locations at which special commands need to be inserted into the final program code for FPH operations, namely (a) Tow feed, (b) Tow start, (c) Tow cut and (d) Tow stop. The state changes that each of the above commands trigger are explained in the control system section of this paper.

Finally, a well sorted and sequenced list with all the generated target points (with their planes or frames) is fed into a toolpath creator tool that interprets them corresponding to user given motion conditions (speed, reference system, tool data, etc) to generate the toolpath data. Steps of the path design are as shown in the Figure 4 in the order (a)-(f).

Figure 4: Path design flow representation for 0-degree layup in the order (a) to (f).

3.4 Digital Path Generation

In the final step, the toolpath data is used to simulate motion of the FPH through the various targets in a stepwise fashion, to check for any unexpected manoeuvres, collisions or incorrect/unreachable orientations/positions.

Figure 5: (a) Iteration that has passed the simulation test (b) Iteration that has failed the simulation test.

Figure 5 shows two iterations of the simulation test, where a previously generated toolpath (b) has failed the test (visualized in red) due to detection of target point or points within the generated toolpath data that are unreachable and/or causes a collision (between parts of the robot). This is rectified by relocating the test mould to a more favourable position (a). An overview in the form of a flowchart for the different stages of the robotic fibre placement process and the toolpath generation process is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Overview of a typical robotic fibre placement operation.

Only if the generated data passes the simulation test, it is fed through an inverse kinematic solver, and then to the robot language code generator of choice, to get the final offline program file. This final program file, which is in the language that the robot can interpret, can then be uploaded to the industrial robot's controller for the final fibre placement operation. Figure 7 shows the target points and toolpath obtained using the algorithm.

Figure 7: Generated toolpath for 0-degree layup on the curved test mould.

4 CONTROL SYSTEM

The robotic fiber placement system has two separate processing units or controllers, with communications links established between them. The KUKA KR 60 robot is controlled by the KUKA KRC4 through a Human machine Interface (HMI) or teach pendant. The FPH is controlled by a Beckhoff IPC (Industrial personal computer) through a touch enabled Beckhoff HMI. Dominating influential parameters, which are the power of the Infrared (IR) lamp (corresponding to required maximum temperatures) and the compaction force are set through the FPH's touch Interface panel before program run. Figure 8 shows the components of the control system.

Figure 8: Components of the fibre placement machine's control system.

Once the layup sequence is simulated and collision avoidance is tested successfully on the offline computer, the generated KUKA robotic language (KRL) program file is transferred to KUKA controller for execution. Commands within this program enable signals to be sent to the FPH's IPC to carry out one of the few operations (feeding of tows, releasing of the clamps, cutting of tows, etc.), when defined target points have been reached. The usual sequence of operations is as shown in figure 9, where red, orange and yellow represent the state of motion of the robot as in the case of traffic lights.

Figure 9: Sequential operations carried out by the fiber placement head.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The layup was performed on a 3D printed test mould modelled using the predefined curved surface geometry. The test mould is 300 mm in length and 300 mm wide, with a varying height between 20 mm to 50 mm. The mould was affixed to the worktable and secured in position using fasteners.

Apart from limitations induced by the machine’s working setup on the toolpath, the quality of the layup obtained using this technique can also depend on other factors derived from properties of the layup material (towpreg) and the layup process conditions. During a couple of test runs, the towpreg material would not adhere to the surface of the mould to form the first layer. Therefore, in such cases, it is important to ensure that the conditions in which the towpreg is used at the time of layup is as per recommended by the manufacturer. The towpreg must exhibit the required level of tackiness to adhere properly to the surface, immediately and only when it exits the fiber placement head. The trick here is to identify the perfect control between the tackiness property and the compaction force.

The towpreg used in this study is by Hexcel and uses the M21 epoxy resin matrix system (thermosetting system) with a content ratio of 34% by weight (M21/34%/UD194/IMA-12K). Tows of width 6.35mm were used.

Figure 10: A frame of the simulated lay-up process from the virtual environment.

Before the experimental placement process, the sequence of movements that iterate the layup process is simulated and thoroughly checked for abnormalities. This is done using the grasshopper plugin for rhinoceros, along with a robot kinematics plugin from HAL robotics, which is the same environment used to develop and generate the toolpath. Together, the placement process is run in a virtual environment and verified to be safe for execution. Figure 10 shows a frame of the simulated layup process.

Following this step, a dry run (without towpregs) of the placement process at reduced speed is done to validate the correctness and accuracy of tool movements that follow the path, with the roller being in constant and continuous contact with the surface of the mould along the generated layup path. Once verified, the placement process is executed with towpregs. Figure 11 shows the fiber placement process employed.

Figure 11: Lay-up on the curved test part; (a) moving between intermediate points; (b), (c) during layup.

For validation of the placement quality, gaps between each course or tow on the test surface were investigated. Gaps between courses in the different plies or layers vary between 0 mm and 2 mm. Overlapping courses were also observed. These defects were identified to be due to the design of the FPH as well as the material properties of the towpreg, where slight slippage was observed initially during the placement process at different compaction conditions (10-15 kg). This can be rectified by optimizing the compaction force applied with respect to the tackiness observed from the towpreg at the time of placement. Figure 12 (a) shows the tow placement achieved in the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th plies with orientation of 45, -45, 90 and 0 degrees respectively.

Figure 12: (a) First, second, third and fourth ply placement on the mould; (b), (c) Surface of the completed layup.

Good adhesion of the first layer onto the test surface was also achieved through optimum pressure control of the compaction roller. Perfect adhesion of the following layers was also achieved, thanks to the repeated compaction of tows of the new layer, onto tows in the previous layer, as can be seen in figure 13 (b) and (c).

Figure 13: (a) Front view and (b) back view of the layup with the mould .

The excess length of tows observed from figure 12, are due to the minimum tow length requirement for layup as dictated by the fiber placement system's design. This is unavoidable, due to the basic working principles based on which the placement technique for this type of additive manufacturing technology was developed. Hence, the actual region or area covered by the placement process is and will be more than the intended in most cases.

6 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Robotic fibre placement technology offers the highest precision and flexibility in composite fabrication. Quality improvements in the part could be foreseen through the implementation of this type of additive manufacturing technique. The simulation-based offline programming approach used to develop and generate the toolpath proved to be effective. The “projection algorithm” developed was implemented and tested both in simulation and practical.

Placement of tows in orientations of 45, -45, 90, 0 was achieved on the test surface. Placement of tows at arbitrary trajectories can also be achieved. All tests were conducted on the same curved surface or test mould. Quality of the placement achieved was checked and assessed.

Ongoing research include the toolpath planning for tubular parts using an external rotary axis. Figure 14 shows a frame from this ongoing toolpath research.

Figure 14: Toolpath for tubular moulds from the virtual environment.

The next step would be to study the effects and influence of different layup speeds on the placement process as well as on the quality of layup observed. The data obtained will be used to identify defects and implement possible fixes through re-designed placement paths or alternative algorithms. The objective of this study would be to reduce machining time and costs, through higher layups speeds. An optimization procedure for the fibre placement process will also be developed for the current setup. Furthermore, through the installation of a thermal imaging camera, experiments to detect gaps or voids during the layup process (in real time) will be also implemented.

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